

ISic0491

I.Sicily inscription 0491

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mazara

Place of origin (modern)

Mazara del Vallo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mazara del Vallo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1

: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2

: mm

Text

1. [L(ucio)AmatioL(uci)f(ilio)Fab(ia)(tribu)]
2. [MaximoMemoriano]
3. [q(uaestori)p(ro)p(raetore)aediliIiviropraef(ecto)]
4. [imp(eratoris)AntoniniIiviri]
5. [Y CENATAI M]
6. [I PRINAXONIAE X FR]
7. [populusLilybitanus]
8. [bonocivi]
9. [l(ocus) p(ublice) d(atus) d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)]

Apparatus

Text after Mommsen in CIL

Ivir QuinquennaliXprimo, Mommsen app. crit.

Translation

Commentary

The stone is described by Mommsen, who located it, as being 'evanida

tota' ('completely worn') and so 'agnovi, sed describi iam non potest' ('I observed it, but it is no longer possible to transcribe it'). Mommsen's text is a best effort, based upon the earlier antiquarian transcriptions. If Mommsen's conjecture for line 6 is correct, this provides additional evidence for the presence of decemprimi at Mazara/Lilybaeum alongside CIL 10.7236 (cf. Manganaro 1988, p.43)

Digital identifiers:

TM 491717

EDCS 22000797

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7211 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 43

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